

Survey on the Attitudes and Awareness of the CNR Scientific Community on Secondary Publishing Right and Authors' Rights Retention

Presentation of Results

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along with

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Abstract

This Report analyses the outcomes of the survey conducted within the National Research Council (CNR) scientific community under the [Right2Pub](#) project - *Balancing Publication Rights: The voice of the scientific community on rights retention and secondary publishing right* (hereafter referred to as “Right2Pub”) financed by the international initiative [Knowledge Rights 21](#) (KR21).

Right2Pub is promoted by the [Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche \(IGSG-CNR\)](#), along with [Biblioteca "Dario Nobili" dell'Area della ricerca CNR di Bologna](#), [Biblioteca e Centro di documentazione scientifica dell'Area della ricerca CNR di Pisa](#), [Creative Commons Italian Chapter](#) and the [Knowledge Rights 21 National Coordinator for Italy](#).

The survey consists of a questionnaire and two focus groups. It aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of researchers’ attitudes and awareness on the topic of copyright, focusing on the secondary publishing right and authors’ rights retention.

The collected data provide a valuable output to future initiatives, including legislative ones, concerning the management and regulation of author’s rights, with a perspective of open and shared access to knowledge. The Report emphasises significant findings from the survey, focusing on the authors’ needs. Additionally, it highlights relevant information for developing a practical guide designed for researchers to implement the rights retention strategy for scientific publications.

The Right2Pub project’s survey represents an initial step towards guiding future interventions and initiatives. It contributes to describing the scientific community’s practices within the project’s scope, addressing its needs and uncertainties.

1. The Context

The scientific publishing landscape demands careful consideration of the dynamics involving scholars as authors and, consequently, copyright holders. Copyright is automatically conferred to the author for every intellectual creation. Safeguarding copyright becomes crucial not only to preserve the integrity of scientific work but also to ensure the unrestricted dissemination of research results, contributing to the progress of knowledge. In Italy, Law No. 633 of April 22, 1941, amended over the years including through European Union legislation, serves as the legal framework governing copyright. This legislation encompasses three main categories of rights: moral rights, economic exploitation rights, and related rights. Moral rights grant the author the right to claim authorship and oppose any modification or distortion or harm that could compromise their reputation. Economic exploitation rights allow the author to control the commercial use of the work, including its publication, reproduction, distribution, communication to the public, and making it available to the public. Finally, related rights protect the legal interests of certain persons and legal entities that contribute to making works available to the public or that produce subject matter which, while not qualifying as works under the copyright systems of all countries, contains sufficient creativity or technical and organizational skill to justify recognition of a copyright-like property right (such as performing artists and producers of audiovisual materials).

Scholars are not always aware of the rights associated with their research outputs or the obligations related to managing these rights imposed by funding bodies, including the European Commission. The authors regularly transfer all their economic exploitation rights to the publishers, or they do not retain sufficient rights that allow them or their funders to republish or reuse their own outputs. This practice contradicts the primary goal of research, which is to maximize its impact by sharing results as widely and promptly as possible. One reason authors licence or transfer their rights is associated with research evaluation practices and career advancement processes, which have thus far, effectively, attributed greater value to publications in commercial publishing venues that often demand the exclusive rights from authors.

Moreover, the issue of copyright management plays a central role in research funding strategies by numerous public and private entities, requiring beneficiaries not to exclusively transfer those rights to commercial publishers. Commercial publishers typically impose high costs for accessing research results, usually in the form of journal subscription fees.

Mechanisms and strategies to encourage scholars to retain specific exploitation rights have been in place for many years. Author addenda modifying publisher contracts were introduced around 2004, with the first funder policies incorporating rights retention provisions initiated by the Wellcome Trust and the National Institutes of Health. In 2008, Harvard University implemented an Open Access (OA)¹ policy, whereby professors grant non-exclusive rights to the institution, enabling the free accessibility of academic articles through its institutional repository. Many institutions worldwide have adopted similar policies in the last 15 years; Europe, in particular, has experienced significant development in OA policies over the last 20 years but has paid less attention to developing policies and practices for retaining rights by scholars.

A significant step forward, especially in this regard, is the launch of the Rights Retention Strategy by cOAlition S in 2021².

In the following year, the European Commission initiated a study³ analysing the role of EU copyright rules in facilitating or hindering access and reuse of scientific publications, including the OA approach. The study explores access and reuse, examining possibilities allowed by exceptions and limitations to copyright in the current legal framework, as well as the framework of fundamental rights underlying these exceptions and limitations. Based on the analysis, the study provides recommendations, assuming that «without access, there can be no re-use, and without re-use, access loses much of its purpose».

Another decisive signal is the Council of the European Union’s Conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, reliable, and fair academic publishing⁴ of May 2023. It welcomed the introduction of secondary publishing right by some Member States in their national copyright legislation. The Council encourages the Commission and Member States to promote policies

¹ <https://osc.hul.harvard.edu/policies/>.

² <https://www.coalition-s.org/resources/rights-retention-strategy/>.

³ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Angelopoulos, C., *Study on EU copyright and related rights and access to and reuse of scientific publications, including open access – Exceptions and limitations, rights retention strategies and the secondary publication right*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022 - <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/891665>.

⁴ <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9616-2023-INIT/en/pdf>.

for a non-profit academic publishing approach characterised by OA and a variety of formats, with no costs for authors or readers. Some Member States have introduced provisions in their national copyright laws granting authors secondary publishing right (compared to the original publication with commercial publishers) for OA to publicly funded research outputs. This right prevails over any contrary contractual provisions. The Council also supports national policies and guidelines on OA, aiming to make research outputs immediately accessible under open licences.

Within this context, the Right2Pub Project aims to support the legislative recognition in Italy of secondary publishing right and increase awareness and sensitivity among the national scientific community regarding the author's rights retention. A deep understanding of the rights related to scientific production and awareness of how to manage these rights constitute the first step to consciously promote scientific progress and protect researchers' individual interests.

II. Survey objectives

The survey seeks to investigate the views of both the scientific community and research support staff at the National Research Council (CNR) regarding copyright. It specifically concentrates on aspects pertaining to the secondary publishing right and authors' rights retention. To gain a deeper understanding of relevant issues related to the management of copyright, two distinct data collection methods have been employed:

1. An **online questionnaire** was distributed to CNR scientific community (researchers and technologists) through the dedicated platform called CNR Survey⁵ (the questionnaire is attached as Appendix).
2. Two separate **focus groups** were organised to engage CNR research support staff.

III. The Questionnaire

A. Data and Methodology

A.1. Description of the questionnaire and of survey process

The survey has been designed from scratch to develop a comprehensive overview of the level of awareness and understanding of copyright issues among the scientific community of CNR. Particular attention has been paid to the themes of secondary publishing right and rights retention.

The survey's goal was to outline a representative framework of prevailing attitudes and specific needs within the scientific community, beyond the initiatives taken by CNR at the

⁵ <https://survey.cnr.it/>.

institutional level. CNR indeed demonstrates significant commitment to the promotion and dissemination of scientific knowledge⁶.

Despite the extensive availability of literature and the vast number of informational resources on various aspects related to copyright management, there remains a dearth of systematic empirical analysis on the subject. The questionnaire was designed with the objective of establishing a solid informational basis for planning and implementing initiatives aimed at promoting informed management of authors' rights during the publication and dissemination of research results, including dynamics related to funded projects.

The collected information is essential, first and foremost, to outline in detail the level of awareness of the respondents and practices regarding the management of CNR authors' rights. Secondly, the questionnaire is useful for generating data that allow for comparison with other national contexts.

In this Section the questionnaire's population (A.1.1.), its structure (A.1.2.), and the dissemination methods (A.1.3.) are described.

A.1.1. Questionnaire Population

The target group of the questionnaire is represented by the scientific community of CNR, which, due to its distinctly inter- and multidisciplinary nature, plays a fundamental role in Italy. This community includes researchers and technologists who constitute a vital resource for the pursuit of the CNR's objectives. In this context, they represent professionals with autonomy and responsibility in carrying out their research activities. Researchers are characterised by the ability to make significant, original, and valuable advancements in knowledge within their disciplinary field. Technologists are experts in translating scientific discoveries into practical applications, and their roles may include tasks such as designing and implementing prototypes and managing technology transfer processes.

The questionnaire was sent to **6,275 researchers and technologists** belonging to the 88 institutes of CNR (as of November 10, 2023). These institutes cover the entire spectrum of ERC (European Research Council) domains and are distributed across the national territory, as illustrated in Figure 1.

⁶ In 2012, the CNR formally endorsed the "Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities," and in 2013, it signed a "Position statement" on open access to research outcomes in Italy. In December 2018, the Open Access Working Group (GdLOA) for CNR research products was established, which approved two significant documents in 2022: the institutional policy and the management policy on open access to CNR scientific literature products. In April 2023, the "Roadmap for CNR's Open Science" was approved in alignment with the National Plan for Open Science. The CNR actively participates in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), promoting its development and supporting international collaboration initiatives. Furthermore, it is engaged in defining new research evaluation models and in Open Science within CoPER, the Consultative Council of Presidents of National Public Research Bodies (EPR), to facilitate coordination on open science among EPRs and Italian universities.

Figure 1: Size and distribution of the institutes of the National Research Council (CNR) and researchers in Italy.

Each of the **88 institutes of CNR** belongs to one of the seven disciplinary Departments that carry out the scientific activities for CNR. Below is the distribution of the scientific community by Department (the numbers refer to the researchers/technologists from the institutes affiliated with each Department):

<i>Earth System Science and Environmental Technologies</i>	1,126
<i>Bio-Agrofood Sciences</i>	669
<i>Chemical Sciences and Materials Technologies</i>	755
<i>Physical Sciences and Materials Technologies</i>	1,057
<i>Biomedical Sciences</i>	972
<i>Engineering, ICT, and Technologies for Energy and Transport</i>	1,073
<i>Humanities and Social Sciences, Cultural Heritage</i>	623

The distribution of personnel across different Departments highlights the representation of diverse scientific disciplines within the CNR community involved in the survey.

A.1.2. Questionnaire Structure

It was crucial to develop a questionnaire with a carefully designed structure. The limited time available and the lack of immediate interest in these topics made it imperative for the questionnaire to be quick and easily navigable, with the goal of encouraging participation. The questionnaire was administered anonymously and required minimal personal information, necessary only to identify the respondent's position within CNR. Additionally, the option to write some free-text comments was provided.

The length and design of the questionnaire were therefore subjects of discussion and analysis within the Right2Pub Project working group, as was the decision to integrate free-text responses sparingly to ease the analysis burden. This strategic approach effectively balanced the need for detailed information with the limited time availability of the research community involved.

In addition to a set of introductory questions (Section A), three separate sections were proposed:

- A. Introductory questions
- B. Information on scientific production
- C. Partial or full republication of research outputs
- D. Level of awareness and understanding of copyright

To ensure a consistent understanding of the thematic context among participants from all ERC domains, it seemed appropriate to provide a glossary of terminology at the beginning of the questionnaire to facilitate respondents in completing it. Below are the proposed definitions:

(a) By *contributo [output]* we mean: article/essay in a peer-reviewed journal, chapter in a volume, monograph, conference proceedings (in a journal or volume).

(b) By *diritto di ripubblicazione in ambito scientifico [secondary publishing right]* we mean: the right to republish research outputs produced as a result of research conducted entirely or partially with public funding in an open-access archive or elsewhere, parallel to their original publication.

(c) By *Ricerche realizzate interamente o parzialmente con finanziamento pubblico [research conducted entirely or partially with public funding]*, we mean: research funded by public entities external to the researcher's affiliated institution.

(d) By *conservazione dei diritti [rights retention]* we mean: the practice of retaining adequate rights for research outputs produced by an institution's researchers, enabling the author to make them immediately accessible and reusable.

(e) By *sede editoriale [publishing venue]* we mean: the publishing house, journal, series, online platform where the authors publish their research outputs.

(f) By *preprint* we mean: the version of an output submitted to the publisher before undergoing the review process (initial version submitted to the publisher; submitted manuscript).

(g) By *postprint* we mean: the version of an output accepted for publication after the review process, excluding the layout or graphic format of the publishing venue (author accepted manuscript, final version submitted by the author to the publisher).

Before distribution, the questionnaire underwent testing in two ways: through an apparent validity test and a full test. The apparent validity test was conducted to check the clarity and precision of the questionnaire's questions, with the participation of seven volunteers. The predominant feedback was that the questionnaire was too long and, consequently, at risk of a high abandonment rate. Additionally, volunteers suggested some minor improvements related to language clarity, coherence, detail level, and question order.

The full questionnaire test was conducted by four researchers from different disciplinary areas, suggesting reducing the questionnaire and rephrasing some questions and response options.

As a result of the tests, the decision was made to eliminate all questions considered too detailed or technical, leading to a reduction in the number of questions from 30 to 26.

A.1.3. Questionnaire distribution

The survey was conducted using CNR Survey software and distributed to recipients through the CNR distribution list (mailing list of researchers and technologists). The use of this software facilitated an efficient data collection process, contributing to the overall success of the survey initiative.

The invitation email was sent on November 10, 2023, and the questionnaire remained available until November 30, 2023. On November 20, 2023, a reminder was also sent to prompt participation. Additionally, the questionnaire link was shared through the CNR website⁷ and CNR's X account⁸ and published on the open science.it website, an Italian gateway dedicated to Open Science⁹.

Personalized invitations were also sent to some Department Directors, who showed willingness to collaborate. This approach aimed to maximize survey participation, leveraging both mass distribution through the mailing list and the targeted involvement of Department Directors.

Below is the invitation message sent to the mailing list of the CNR research community.

⁷ <https://www.cnr.it/it/news/12354/partecipa-all-indagine-sui-diritti-dell-autore-nel-processo-di-pubblicazione-scientifica>.

⁸ <https://twitter.com/CNRsocial/status/1726590946811490657/>.

⁹ <https://open-science.it/-/cnr-avviata-una-indagine-sui-diritti-d-autore-nel-processo-di-pubblicazione-scientifica>.

Dear colleagues,

The Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems (IGSG) and the Libraries of the Research Area of Pisa and the Research Area of Bologna invite you to participate in the survey on copyright in the scientific publishing process. The survey is part of the "Balancing Publication Rights" project (Right2Pub), funded by the international initiative Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21), aimed at supporting the secondary publishing right in the scientific field, advocating for legislative change at the national level.

*We kindly ask you to complete the questionnaire available at the following link:
<https://survey.cnr.it/index.php?r=survey/index&sid=181682>*

The deadline is November 30, 2023, and the estimated time to answer the questions is approximately 10 minutes. The questionnaire is anonymous. It is addressed to the entire scientific community of CNR, and your participation is crucial to obtaining a comprehensive and representative overview of our community's knowledge and awareness on copyright issues.

We thank you in advance for your valuable collaboration, which will significantly contribute to the success of this initiative. Furthermore, based on the data gleaned from the questionnaire, proposals for legislative changes aimed at ensuring authors have complete control over the timing and methods of publishing their research outputs will be pursued.

*Thank you, with warmest regards,
The research group of the Right2Pub project*

A.2. Numbers of Answers

The data collection process resulted in a total of **889 completed questionnaires (corresponding to 14% of those invited)**, with an additional 309 responses initiated but not submitted due to respondents failing to click the "Submit Responses" button at the end of the questionnaire. The unsubmitted responses varied in completeness, but it was found that the majority of them could be disregarded as they contained little or no data of substantive value.

B. Results

B.1. Responses to Section A – Introductory questions

Q1. Select Your age band

69.5% of respondents (618 individuals) fall within the age band of 40 to 59 years (specifically, 33.4% in the 40-49 age band and 36.1% in the 50-59 age band); the remaining percentage is roughly evenly distributed between the age bands of 30 to 39 years (14.6%) and 60 years or older (15.6%). Only 2 respondents are younger than 30 years.

Q2. Specify the years of Your scientific activity (intended as years since the first publication)

71% of respondents have a duration of scientific activity (years elapsed since the date of the first publication) ranging from 11 to 30 years (specifically, 35% from 11 to 20 years and 36% from 21 to 30 years). Overall, the vast majority of respondents have a considerable level of

experience (only 11% have an experience that does not exceed 10 years of activity since the first publication).

Q3. Specify Your professional level

63% of respondents hold the entry-level position in the research career at CNR (researcher/technologist), and 13% of respondents are at the top level of their career (research director/technology director). The intermediate level (senior researcher/senior technologist) is occupied by 24% of respondents.

Considering the relationship between the qualifications of the invitees and those declared by the respondents, research directors showed the highest interest in the questionnaire (18.2% of the 588 research directors who received the invitation completed the questionnaire). Less interest was observed among technologists at the three professional levels (with the participation rate of each level never exceeding 7%).

Q4. Specify Your CNR Department of affiliation

Regarding the distribution of respondents in relation to the department of affiliation, the most represented departments are, in order: *Earth system sciences and technologies for the environment* (17.66% of respondents belong to this department); Engineering, ICT, and technologies for energy and transport (16.76%) and *Physical sciences and technologies of matter* (16.09%). Considering the affiliations to the departments of the invitees, researchers/technologists who have shown the most interest in responding to the questionnaire are those from the department of *Humanities and Social Sciences, Cultural Heritage* (18% of those affiliated with the department responded to the questionnaire).

Q5. Specify the scientific disciplinary field of Your research (select the main ERC research field or fields)

Each respondent could indicate multiple areas of interest. Respondents made a total of 1,379 choices (see Table 1). The most represented ERC domain is PE–Physical Sciences and Engineering, followed by LS–Life Sciences, and finally by SH–Social Sciences and Humanities (in this last case, 128 respondents have indicated at least one SH research field among those of interest).

LS1 Molecules of Life: Biological Mechanisms, Structures and Functions	82	9.22%
LS2 Integrative Biology: from Genes and Genomes to Systems	33	3.71%
LS3 Cell Biology, Development, Stem Cells and Regeneration	28	3.15%
LS4 Physiology in Health, Disease and Ageing	26	2.92%
LS5 Neuroscience and Disorders of the Nervous System	38	4.27%
LS6 Immunity, Infection and Immunotherapy	13	1.46%
LS7 Prevention, Diagnosis and Treatment of Human Diseases	39	4.39%
LS8 Environmental Biology, Ecology and Evolution	74	8.32%
LS9 Biotechnology and Biosystems Engineering	63	7.09%
PE1 Mathematics	29	3.26%
PE10 Earth System Science	141	15.86%
PE11 Materials Engineering	84	9.45%
PE2 Fundamental Constituents of Matter	23	2.59%
PE3 Condensed Matter Physics	110	12.37%
PE4 Physical and Analytical Chemical Sciences	89	10.01%
PE5 Synthetic Chemistry and Materials	80	9.00%
PE6 Computer Science and Informatics	107	12.04%
PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering	70	7.87%
PE8 Products and Processes Engineering	55	6.19%
PE9 Universe Sciences	9	1.01%
SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations	14	1.57%
SH2 Institutions, Governance and Legal Systems	24	2.70%
SH3 The Social World and Its Interactions	27	3.04%
SH4 The Human Mind and Its Complexity	26	2.92%
SH5 Texts and Concepts	21	2.36%
SH6 The Study of the Human Past: Archaeology and history	29	3.26%
SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	20	2.25%
SH8 Studies of Cultures and Arts	25	2.81%
<i>total selections</i>	1379	

Table 1: ERC Domains selected by the respondents (multiple choices allowed)

B.2. Responses to Section B – information on scientific production

Q6. How many peer-reviewed outputs have You published to date?

A large majority of respondents report a significant experience with peer-reviewed outputs: overall, 77% of respondents have such experience with a number equal to or greater than 26 outputs (specifically, 28% of respondents claim to have published between 51 and 100 peer-reviewed outputs, and 19% claim to have published more than a hundred outputs).

Q7. Indicate the percentage of outputs produced as a result of research carried out entirely or partially with public funding

73% of respondents declare that a significant portion (ranging from 50 to 100%) of their production has been carried out entirely or partially with public funding.

Q8. In the last 10 years, which publication approaches have been most applied to Your outputs?

From the response to this question, which allowed for two choices, it appears that the most applied publication approach for outputs produced by the respondents is the *restricted access* approach, where editorial venues are accessible only through subscription or payment for individual outputs (36.03% of the 1,399 choices made by respondents).

The second most applied approach (25.66%) is that of *Gold Open Access*, in which the author publishes in an editorial venue with all content openly accessible, but it requires a fee.

Following the above, there are *Green Open Access* (21.73%) and *Hybrid Open Access* (11.94%). In the Green approach, the author publishes with restricted access but makes the electronic version (preprint, postprint, publisher's final version) freely available in an institutional or disciplinary archive, respecting any embargo imposed by the publisher. In the Hybrid approach, the author publishes in a subscription-based editorial venue (usually subscribed to by the institution) and, for a fee (APCs - Article Processing Charges), has the option to make the specific output openly accessible; it is also referred to as Hybrid Open Access when the author doesn't cover the costs, but the institution has a transformative agreement with the publisher.

The least applied approach appears to be that of *Diamond open access* (4.65%), where the author publishes in a publishing venue (usually nonprofit) where all content is open access; there are no costs to the author or subscription fees.

B.3. Responses to Section C – Full or partial republication of research outputs

Q9. Given the choice, which type of public domain tool or Creative Commons license do You prefer to be applied to Your outputs?

The data emerging from the responses to this question essentially reveals a limited understanding of Creative Commons licenses. This is evident both explicitly, as 57.8% of respondents declare that they do not exactly know what these licenses are and what the differences between them are, and implicitly, considering that 15% of respondents refer to a type of tool (CC0) for dedicating their work to the public domain. CC0 is distinct from the concept of a licence and may not be well-suited for scientific outputs, as it implies the author’s waiver of all economic rights to the work.

Q10. When You publish Your output, do You worry about verifying which rights You retain?

55% of respondents, by answering "no" to the question, declare that they do not worry about checking which rights they retain on their works when they publish.

Q11. If yes [i.e., You concern with verifying which rights You retain], how?

76% of those who are concerned about verifying the rights they retain on their work when publishing state that they do so by reading the contractual clauses to understand the exact conditions specified, while 16% declare that they refrain from publishing with the specific publisher if they find the contractual conditions unsatisfactory.

Q12. Once Your output is published in a commercial publishing venue, what do You do to republish it?

40% of respondents declare not to republish the output published in a commercial publishing venue due to the difficulties of requesting authorization from the publisher (in cases where the publisher’s policies do not allow republication without specific authorization). An overwhelming majority of the remaining 60% seeks the publisher’s authorization or checks the publisher’s consent through the SHERPA ROMEO database. 10% of respondents republish without bothering to seek authorization from the commercial publisher.

Q13. Are You aware of the difference between “Version of Record” and “Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM)” in the context of republishing an output?

75% of respondents declare not to know the difference between “Version of Record” and “Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM)” in the context of republishing an output.

Q14. How important are the following republication methods to You?

Among the various methods of republishing an output, those considered most relevant are the immediate deposit (zero embargo) of the postprint in the institutional or disciplinary repository and the use of other republication venues (e.g., academic platforms, professional networks, personal websites), considered highly relevant by 41% and 36% of respondents, respectively.

Inserting the output into a teaching handout and using parts of the output in a new publication (print or electronic) are considered not very relevant or not relevant by the respondents.

Q15. In case You deposit the output, how often do You do it?

From the responses to this question, a different approach of respondents emerges regarding the frequency of the deposit, depending on the methods used: only 10% declare to always deposit the output in preprint archives, compared to 27% who always deposit in institutional repositories.

Q16. What is the main reason that drives You to deposit Your output?

Just over half of the respondents (52%) consider the main reason for depositing their output to be the desire to make research freely available to all; the remaining three options (because it is required by funding agencies, to improve scientific collaboration, to make researchers' activities known and verifiable) have essentially the same weight in the respondents' opinion.

B.4. Responses to Section D - Level of awareness and understanding of copyright

Q17. How would You describe your interest in copyright-related issues?

34% of respondents declare having low or no interest in copyright-related issues, while only 17% claim to have a high level of interest.

Q18. How would You rate your level of knowledge on these topics?

In the respondents, there is a prevailing lack of knowledge regarding copyright issues relevant to the survey. The option of "poor knowledge" concerning the transfer of commercial exploitation rights to the publisher, the author's ability to retain certain rights to their research outputs, and the author's rights within the framework of Italian copyright law is around 50%, while the option of "no knowledge" for the same topics is selected by approximately 20% of respondents.

However, there seems to be greater awareness regarding the topic of republication of research outputs: while 44% exhibit poor knowledge, there is also a 10% acknowledgement of good understanding of the subject.

Q19. To what extent do the following aspects of editorial policies influence Your choice of publication venue for Your outputs?

Q20. What role do the rules governing the national research evaluation system play in Your choice of publication venue?

70% of respondents declare that they also base their choice of publication venue for their outputs on the rules governing the national research evaluation system (considered highly or quite relevant for this choice).

Q21. Are You aware of the Rights Retention Strategy promoted by cOAlition S, a consortium composed of research funding organisations from various European countries?

95% of respondents are not aware of the Rights Retention Strategy promoted by cOAlition S.

Q22. Are You familiar with the ongoing debate at the European Union level on the topics of transparent, open, reliable, and fair scientific publishing (Council conclusions of the European Union approved on May 23, 2023)?

68% of respondents are not familiar with the ongoing debate at the European Union level on the topics of transparent, open, reliable, and fair scientific publishing.

Q23. Do You know that in 2018 a bill containing a provision on Open Access to scientific publications was presented?

80% of respondents do not know that in 2018 a bill containing a provision on Open Access to scientific publications was presented.

Q24. Are You aware that there are countries where there is an explicit right of secondary publishing in the scientific field recognized by law?

85% of respondents are not aware that there are countries where there is an explicit secondary publishing right in the scientific field recognized by law.

Q25. Would You support the submission of a bill that recognizes the right to immediately republish a publicly funded output as Open Access (zero embargo)?

The vast majority of respondents expressed support for the submission of the bill (81%).

In the free-text comments of those who declared themselves in favour, it was emphasised, among other things, that provisions regulating the secondary publishing right already exist in some European countries.

Overall, the driving reasons behind the choice lie in the importance of broad dissemination and accessibility of scientific research and knowledge funded by public funds.

Eliminating the embargo on publication could ensure that research results are immediately available to the scientific community and the general public, accelerating scientific progress and facilitating collaboration among researchers.

While supporting the submission of the proposal, the following observations were made:

- The costs of Open Access should not burden authors or affect already limited research funding: for example, it was proposed that these costs be borne by the institution of origin through agreements with publishers.
- There is a need to change the way publications are evaluated: respondents emphasise, for example, the need not to give greater value to subscription-based journals compared to those in Open Access.
- It would be necessary to incentivize publishers by providing them with better evaluation in case of consent to republishing in Open Access: the importance of promoting institutional forms of scientific publishing is emphasised, among other things.

Only a small portion of respondents (9%) expressed opposition to the submission of the bill because they would prefer a broader rule (everything and immediately Open Access). In general, it should be noted that issues related to the distribution of Open Access costs and

the need to promote institutional scientific publishing that guarantees republishing were reiterated even by some of those who did not support this position.

Finally, among the comments of respondents who declared themselves uninterested or did not consider legislation addressing the issue of immediate Open Access republication of publicly funded outputs necessary, there were concerns that journals that historically have built their prestige based on the quality of reviewers, professionalism of editors, and implemented policies could be somehow damaged by such legislation. In fact, it was observed that the proliferation of open-access journals could lower the level of control and responsibility over publications and, at the same time, their quality and originality.

Overall, there is a need for specific training and clear guidelines to facilitate understanding of various editorial policies and the consequent choice of republication venue for one's output.

Q26. Would You be interested in further exploring the topics covered in the questionnaire by participating in dedicated training events?

71% of respondents answered yes.

C. Summary of Questionnaire's results

Age and scientific seniority (Q1, Q2): The distribution of responses related to age and scientific seniority reveals a profile dominated by researchers and technologists with consolidated experience. 69.5% of respondents fall in the age range of 40 to 59 years, while 71% have scientific seniority between 11-30 years. This highlights that respondents are characterised by maturity and significant experience in the field of research.

Professional level and department of affiliation (Q3, Q4): 63% of respondents are at the entry-level of the research personnel career, while 24% are at the intermediate level. Research directors show particular interest, with a participation rate of 18.2% compared to the invited participants. Furthermore, the distribution in departments highlights a strong representation in Earth System Sciences, Engineering, ICT and Technologies for Energy, and Physical Sciences and Technologies of Matter.

Disciplinary area (Q5): Responses to the question about the disciplinary area of research reveal a diversification of interests, covering all ERC domains (also with a multidisciplinary approach, as many respondents indicated more than one disciplinary area of interest). PE–Physical Sciences and Engineering is the most represented ERC domain.

Experience in scientific publishing (Q6, Q7, Q8): The majority of respondents have extensive experience in scientific publishing, with 77% having published 26 or more referee-reviewed outputs. The preference for paid publishing approaches, such as restricted access and Gold Open Access, suggests a need to explore financial strategies to support Open Access.

Creative Commons licences (Q9, Q10, Q11): There is a lack of knowledge about Creative Commons licences, with 57.8% of participants declaring they do not know exactly what these licences are. The question about verifying rights on one's work indicates that 55% of respondents are not concerned with this issue when publishing.

Secondary publishing right (Q12, Q13): 40% of respondents avoid republishing outputs published in commercial venues due to difficulties in obtaining authorization. The lack of

awareness about the difference between “Version of Record” and “Author Accepted Manuscript” is evident in 75% of negative responses to the question on this topic.

Methods of republication (Q14, Q15): The most relevant republication method is the immediate deposit of the postprint in institutional archives. However, only 10% of those who declare to make the deposit always do so in preprint archives, whereas 27% declare to always deposit in institutional or disciplinary archives.

Interest and awareness of copyright (Q17, Q18, Q19): 34% declare to have no or low interest in copyright-related issues. Regarding knowledge of specific copyright topics, respondents declare poor or no competence (highlighting the need for continuous education). However, it is worth noting that the topic of secondary publishing is more widely known compared to others.

Influence of editorial policies and knowledge of foreign initiatives (Q19, Q20, Q21, Q22, Q23, Q24): The choice of publication venue is primarily influenced by editorial policies regarding the use of open licences. However, the lack of knowledge about initiatives like cOAlition S’s Rights Retention Strategy and the debate on open science in Europe indicates the need for more information on the *supranational* and international scene.

Support for Open Access legislation proposals (Q25): The majority of participants (81%) would support the presentation of a bill recognizing the right to immediately republish in Open Access outputs funded with public funds. However, concerns arise about cost distribution and the need to preserve the quality of scientific publishing.

Interest in training events (Q26): 71% of respondents are interested in participating in training events dedicated to the questionnaire’s themes, highlighting a willingness to deepen knowledge on publishing issues and copyright.

C.1. In-depth Analysis: Respondents from the disciplinary domains of the ERC SH domain

The collected data lend themselves to in-depth analysis related to specific subgroups of respondents identified on the basis of the responses provided to the questions in section A. For instance, it may be interesting to verify whether individuals in the early stages of their careers exhibit different attitudes compared to those at other professional levels or if different attitudes characterise different age groups.

In this regard, the results of the analysis pertaining to the subgroup characterised by indicating at least one disciplinary domain within the SH domain (Social Sciences and Humanities) as their research area in response to **question 5** are presented below. This subgroup comprises a total of 128 respondents, who demonstrate varying levels of knowledge or attention to certain issues compared to the overall analysis or the subgroup consisting of respondents from the PE and LS sectors.

Specifically, regarding the question posed in **question 8** (publication models most commonly applied to their research outputs), there is a broader utilisation of restricted access publication (41% compared to 35% of respondents from non-SH sectors and 36% overall) and notably the Diamond open access model (18% compared to just over 2% of non-SH respondents and 4.65% overall).

From the responses to **question 9**, a greater familiarity with Creative Commons licences is evident (45% declare not knowing exactly what they are, compared to 60% of non-SH respondents).

A significant finding to consider emerges concerning **question 10** (when publishing a contribution, are you concerned with verifying which rights you retain over your work?): the affirmative response prevails (at 54%) compared to the prevalence of negatives among non-SH respondents (57%).

It is worth noting, furthermore, both (**question 17**) a heightened interest in copyright issues (20% declare a high interest compared to 17% of those who identify outside the SH sectors) and (**question 18**) a greater knowledge on certain topics: copyright within the framework of Italian law (good knowledge at 10% compared to 5% overall) and transfer of exploitation rights to the publisher (good knowledge at 9% compared to 6%).

Additionally, responses to **questions 21 through 24** reveal a generally broader awareness of the national and international debate: the percentage of those responding negatively to the various questions is consistently lower by 6-7 points compared to the overall data for all respondents.

IV. Focus Group

Two Focus Groups were conducted in Pisa and Bologna on December 13 and 14, 2023, respectively. The meetings were organised and conducted by the librarians of the CNR Research Areas of Pisa and Bologna. The Pisa Focus Group involved 7 participants and 2 observers, while the Bologna Focus Group involved 8 participants and 1 observer.

A. Participants

Participants (evenly distributed among roles such as researchers/technologists, librarians/scientific secretaries, technicians) were selected from the CNR personnel supporting the scientific community in depositing products in the People¹¹ institutional repository or during research assessment exercises (VQR - *Valutazione della Qualità della Ricerca*) conducted by the National Agency for the Evaluation of the University and Research System. In this context, it was hypothesised that those involved might have more knowledge on the topic of rights retention related to Open Access to scientific production.

At the beginning of the meeting, participants were asked to introduce themselves and briefly describe their activities related to the Focus Group's themes. In general, a heterogeneous picture emerged in terms of knowledge, expertise, and roles.

The participants in the meetings belong to thirteen CNR Institutes¹².

¹¹ People platform: at the time of conducting the two Focus Groups was the institutional repository of scientific production of CNR. The platform was discontinued on January 31, 2024.

¹² These are the following institutes: IBE - Istituto per la BioEconomia; ICCOM - Istituto di Chimica dei Composti Organometallici; IGG - Istituto di Geoscienze e Georisorse, IIT - Istituto di Informatica e Telematica; IMATI - Istituto di Matematica Applicata e Tecnologie Informatiche "E. Magenes"; IMEM - Istituto dei Materiali per l'Elettronica e il Magnetismo, IMM - Istituto per la Microelettronica e Microsistemi, IN - Istituto di Neuroscienze;

B. Topics covered

Both meetings addressed the following topics:

1. Open Access publishing
2. Knowledge of Authors' rights
3. In-depth knowledge of Authors' rights

For each topic, specific questions were asked. Below, for each set of questions, there is a brief analysis of the discussion, with some verbatim quotes from the participants considered most significant.

B.1. Open Access publishing

- Do researchers at your institute publish in Open Access?
- Are authors provided with instructions and/or provisions regarding Open Access?
- What are the most commonly used methods among self-archiving, paid publication in fully Open Access journals, or hybrid journals? Have you observed any interest in publishing in nonprofit editorial venues, which typically do not involve costs for both authors and readers?

Generally speaking, all participants are aware of issues related to scientific production in Open Access. They all note a general increase in OA publishing following fund disbursement (e.g., PNRR¹³), the signing of transformative agreements by CNR, and obligations agreed upon with funders. The availability of funds is the main factor favouring OA publishing.

Except for some specific contexts involving individual researchers or small research communities, where preprint deposit has been widespread for a long time, participants state that self-archiving is not a common practice for OA.

«Researchers struggle to understand that self-archiving is a way to do OA.» *[quote]*

Diamond OA is not well-known, or at least not widely practised, and the mainly used method is paid Open Access, either Gold or Hybrid.

Although several participants have actively promoted CNR initiatives to encourage OA practices by providing informative materials within the Institute, the primary determinant remains the prestige of the publishing venue.

B.2. Knowledge of Authors' Rights

- Have you ever had the opportunity to review the publishing contract signed by an author with the publisher, or do you know what rights authors typically transfer to publishers in a standard publication contract?

IRCRES - Istituto di Ricerca sulla Crescita Economica Sostenibile; ISAC - Istituto di Scienze dell'Atmosfera e del Clima; ISMN - Istituto per lo Studio dei Materiali Nanostrutturati, ISOF - Istituto per la Sintesi Organica e la Fotoreattività; ISSMC - Istituto di Scienza, Tecnologia e Sostenibilità per lo Sviluppo dei Materiali Ceramici.

¹³ PNRR: The "National Recovery and Resilience Plan" (PNRR) is the plan approved in Italy in 2021 to revive the economy following the COVID-19 pandemic, enabling the country's green and digital transitions. The PNRR is part of the European Union program known as "Next Generation EU".

- Are you aware of tools that authors can use to associate usage licences (such as Creative Commons licences) with their work or tools that can help in retaining some rights (e.g., editorial addenda for reuse for educational purposes, republication of the work in an institutional repository...)?

Most participants state they do not review contracts proposed by publishers because they are not involved in that stage of the publishing process or, if they are authors, they are familiar with the topic but lack a profound awareness of negotiation possibilities with the publisher. For example, through the inclusion of addenda to publishing contracts. Furthermore, to publish in certain venues, they feel they must comply with the publishers' conditions and, therefore, cannot secure greater guarantees for retaining their rights.

«[...] one essentially adapts to the conditions imposed in exchange for a certain type of visibility.» [quote]

Another highlighted difficulty concerns the identification of the version allowed for the deposit.

«[...] a challenging moment was when we had to insert the PDF [full text of the output]. Of what? The published version, the preprint, the post-print; something could be done depending on what the publisher allowed. But recognizing [...] what could be done was [...] a bit complicated for everyone.» [quote]

There is thus a low knowledge and almost no application of addenda, as well as Creative Commons licences, which some are aware of but only superficially.

B.3. In-depth Knowledge of Authors' Rights

- Are you aware that in 2018 a bill containing a provision on Open Access to scientific publications was presented?
- Do you know the difference between Rights Retention Strategy and Secondary Publishing Right?
- Would you be interested in participating in training events dedicated to the topics we have discussed?

Only three participants had heard of the bill in 2018 (so-called "Gallo's Draft Law"). No one claimed to be able to establish the difference between Rights Retention and Secondary Publishing Right. No one was aware of rights retention strategies or policies such as the one promoted by cOAlition S.

Most respondents expressed a willingness to participate in training events dedicated to the topics discussed in the Focus Group. Some suggested creating hands-on activities and "ready-to-use" training materials, focusing on practical aspects and problem-solving.

«I, provocatively, would say that an in-depth study is of no interest to researchers when there is no real power in their hands. So, as long as we are, let's say, under the check of the evaluation system or productivity rules, that we cannot change except with a collective conscience movement. Let's put it that way, I can be the world's greatest expert on all publication policies, but then I will continue to behave as I am, let's say, bound to behave from the point of view of the rules, in this case of the institution [...]. Said in an even more provocative way, I would do it for the leaders of our institution, not for the base.» [quote]

«[...] yes, training is always welcome, but I don't know how much participation it could find.»
 [quote]

C. Summary of Focus Group

The topics of the Focus Groups, although little known and practised, are considered central to the scientific publishing process.

Focus Group participants observe the lack of specific policies and procedures from the institution regarding rights retention and Open Access publishing, which would significantly contribute to increasing the scientific community's awareness and facilitate the management of the publishing process, from negotiation with the publisher.

In addition to what the questions required, other related issues emerged uniformly. For example, there are many references to research assessment exercises, including difficulties encountered, especially regarding the choice of the allowed version for Open Access deposit. Another predominant aspect is the centrality of the criteria used to assess research quality, which strongly influence the selection of publishing venues. Therefore, authors give up negotiating any rights just to publish with prestigious publishers and in high-impact factor journals. Consequently, negotiation is not considered a feasible option.

Furthermore, there is a considerable concern about predatory publishing, linked, on the one hand, to a lack of knowledge of tools to select publishers, and on the other hand, to a lack of clarity and sharing of knowledge and experiences among the involved actors.

Finally, some participants clarified that the choice of the publishing venue may also be influenced by any facilitations authors can receive from publishers, as they are part of the boards of specific journals for which they often also perform peer-review activities.

V. Conclusions

The analysis of data collected through the survey within the CNR research community provides insights into current scientific practices, which may serve as a foundation for further initiatives aligning with the evolving scientific publishing ecosystem.

Copyright awareness – along with collaboration among scientists and the promotion of open science – is indeed to be considered a key pillar for sustainable and shared scientific progress.

Based on the analysis of responses and expressed opinions, we intend to develop, within the framework of the Right2Pub project, recommendations directed at decision-makers aimed at promoting an evolution of copyright legislation in the scientific domain. This evolution should be in line with the goal of consolidating transparency, fairness, openness, and reliability in scientific publishing.

Appendix
Questionnaire

Project Right2Pub - Survey on author rights in the scientific publishing process

This survey is part of the "Balancing Publication Rights" project (Right2Pub), funded by the international initiative Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21), and aims to support the right to secondary publication in the scientific field and the preservation of authors' rights by promoting legislative change at the national level. The project is promoted by the Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems (IGSG), along with the "Dario Nobili" Library of the Bologna Research Area, the Library and Scientific Documentation Center of the Pisa Research Area, and the Italian Chapter of Creative Commons.

Deadline for questionnaire completion: November 30, 2023. Time required: Answering the questionnaire questions takes approximately 10 minutes (you can see all the questions by downloading the PDF version).

Context and objectives: The questionnaire is addressed to researchers and technologists of the CNR, who constitute a fundamental component of the research community in Italy. The aim is to investigate the perception and knowledge of the CNR scientific community regarding copyright, particularly regarding the themes of the right to republish in the scientific field (secondary publication right) and the retention of rights by the author (rights retention).

Definitions: For the purpose of completing the questionnaire, we assume the following definitions:

(a) By *Output* we mean: article/essay in a peer-reviewed journal, chapter in a volume, monograph, conference proceedings (in a journal or volume)..

(b) By *Secondary publishing right* we mean: the right to republish research outputs produced as a result of research conducted entirely or partially with public funding in an open-access archive or elsewhere, parallel to their original publication.

(c) By *Research conducted entirely or partially with public funding* we mean: research funded by public entities external to the researcher's affiliated institution.

(d) By *Rights retention* we mean: the practice of retaining adequate rights for research outputs produced by an institution's researchers, enabling the author to make them immediately accessible and reusable.

(e) By *Publishing venue* we mean: the publishing house, journal, series, online platform where the authors publish their research outputs.

(f) By *Preprint* we mean: the version of an output submitted to the publisher before undergoing the review process (initial version submitted to the publisher; submitted manuscript).

(g) By *Postprint* we mean: the version of an output accepted for publication after the review process, excluding the layout or graphic format of the publishing venue (author accepted manuscript, final version submitted by the author to the publisher).

A. INTRODUCTORY QUESTIONS

Q1. Select Your age band

- Less than 30 years old
- From 30 to 39 years old
- From 40 to 49 years old
- From 50 to 59 years old
- 60 years old or older

Q2. Specify the years of Your scientific activity (intended as years since the first publication)

- From 1 to 10 years old

- From 11 to 20 years old
- From 21 to 30 years old
- From 31 to 40 years old
- More than 41 years old

Q3. Specify Your professional level

- Researcher
- Technologist
- Senior researcher
- Senior technologist
- Research Director
- Technologist Director

Q4. Specify Your CNR Department of affiliation

- Earth system sciences and technologies for the environment
- Bio-agri-food sciences
- Chemical sciences and materials technologies
- Physical sciences and materials technologies
- Biomedical sciences
- Engineering, ICT, and technologies for energy and transportation
- Humanities and social sciences, cultural heritage

Q5. Specify the scientific disciplinary field of Your research (select the main ERC research field or fields).

(allow multiple responses)

B. INFORMATION ON SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

Q6. How many peer-reviewed outputs have you published to date?

- From 1 to 5
- From 6 to 10
- From 11 to 25
- From 26 to 50
- From 51 to 100
- More than 100
- I don't know

Q7. Indicate the percentage of outputs produced as a result of research carried out entirely or partially with public funding

- < 25%
- Between 25% and 50%
- Between 50% and 75%
- Between 75% and 100%

Q8. In the last 10 years, which publication approaches have been most applied to Your outputs?

(allow max two responses)

- *Restricted access publication*: editorial venues accessible only through subscription or payment for individual contributions

- *Green open access*: The author publishes with restricted access, but makes available in open and free access the electronic version (preprint, postprint, publisher's final version) permitted by the publisher (respecting any embargo) in an institutional or disciplinary repository.
- *Diamond open access*: The author publishes in an editorial venue (usually non-profit) where all content is openly accessible; there are no costs to the author or subscription fees.
- *Gold open access*: The author publishes in an editorial venue where all content is openly accessible, but it is necessary to incur a cost for open access.
- *Hybrid open access*: The author publishes in an editorial venue accessible only through subscription (usually subscribed to by the affiliated institution) which offers the author, upon payment (APCs - Article Processing Charges), the option of limited open access publication for the specific contribution. Hybrid open access is also referred to when it is not the author who bears the costs of open access publication, but the affiliated institution that has entered into a transformative agreement with the publisher.

C PARTIAL OR FULL REPUBLICATION OF RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Q9. Given the choice, which type of public domain tool or Creative Commons license do You prefer to be applied to Your outputs? CC BY

- CC0 (public domain)
- CC BY
- CC BY-SA
- CC BY-NC
- CC BY-NC-SA
- CC-BY-ND
- CC-BY-NC-ND
- I found myself having to choose among these licenses, but it's not clear to me what they are and what the differences between them are.

Q10. When You publish Your output, do You worry about verifying which rights You retain?

- Yes
- No

Q11. If yes, how?

- I read the contractual clauses to understand the exact terms and conditions.
- I discuss the contractual clauses with the publisher and potentially request modifications.
- I refrain from publishing with the publisher if I find the conditions unsatisfactory (e.g., due to clauses conflicting with the open access requirements set by the public entity funding the research).
- Other

Q12. Once Your output is published in a commercial publishing venue, what do You do to republish it?

- I republish it without worrying about asking for permission.
- I republish it only if I have verified the publisher's consent in the SHERPA RoMEO database.
- I request permission from the publisher in case their policies do not allow me to republish it without specific authorization.
- I don't republish it because of the difficulty in obtaining permission.

Q13. Are You aware of the difference between “Version of Record” and “Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM)” in the context of republishing an output?

- Yes
- No

Q14. How important are the following republication methods to You?

(Options: Highly relevant, Quite relevant, Not very relevant, Not relevant, I don’t know)

- Immediate deposit (zero embargo) of the postprint in the institutional or disciplinary repository
- Other venues for republication (e.g., academic platforms, professional networks, personal website)
- Inclusion of the contribution in teaching materials
- Use of parts of the contribution in a new publication (print or electronic)
- Inclusion of one or more figures/tables/diagrams in a new publication
- Other (*specify in the text box*)

Q15. In case You deposit the output, how often do You do it?

(Options: Always, Often, Sometimes, Never)

- In preprint archives
- In institutional or disciplinary archives (postprint version)

Q16. What is the main reason that drives You to deposit Your output?

- To make research freely available to everyone
- To enhance scientific collaboration
- To make researchers’ activities known and verifiable (accountability towards society)
- Because it is required by funding agencies

D LEVEL OF AWARENESS AND UNDERSTANDING OF COPYRIGHT

Q17. How would You describe your interest in copyright-related issues?

- High
- Medium
- Low
- Don’t know / No opinion

Q18. How would You rate your level of knowledge on these topics?

(options: Excellent, Good, Sufficient, Poor, None)

- Copyright within the framework of Italian copyright law (L. 633/1941)
- Transfer of exploitation rights to the publisher
- Republication of research outputs
- Possibility of retaining certain rights over research outputs

Q19. To what extent do the following aspects of editorial policies influence Your choice of publication venue for Your outputs?

(Options: Highly relevant, Quite relevant, Not very relevant, Not relevant)

- Possibility of immediate deposit (e.g., is self-archiving of published content possible and under what conditions?)
- Duration of embargo period
- Application of open licenses (CC BY or similar licenses)
- Other relevant aspects (*specify in the text box*)

Q20. What role do the rules governing the national research evaluation system play in Your choice of publication venue?

- Highly relevant
- Quite relevant
- Not very relevant
- Not relevant

Q21. Are You aware of the Rights Retention Strategy promoted by cOAlition S, a consortium composed of research funding organisations from various European countries?

- Yes
- No

Q22. Are You familiar with the ongoing debate at the European Union level on the topics of transparent, open, reliable, and fair scientific publishing (Council conclusions of the European Union approved on May 23, 2023)?

- Yes
- No

Q23. Do You know that in 2018 a bill containing a provision on Open Access to scientific publications was presented?

- Yes
- No

Q24. Are You aware that there are countries where there is an explicit right of secondary publishing in the scientific field recognized by law?

- Yes
- No

Q25. Would You support the submission of a bill that recognizes the right to immediately republish a publicly funded output as Open Access (zero embargo)?

- Yes
- No, because I would like an even broader regulation (everything and also immediately open access)
- No, because I am not interested or do not consider it necessary for regulation to address this issue.

Please comment your selection

Q26. Would You be interested in further exploring the topics covered in the questionnaire by participating in dedicated training events?

- Yes
- No